

Uncatalyzed non-Malapradian periodate oxidation of aromatic amines – An overview[†]

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Abstract : A review of the literature related to the uncatalyzed oxidation of aromatic amines by periodate ion under different conditions is presented. The reports are available from synthesis as well as kinetic point of view. The reports are contradictory in terms of the free radical or ion-dipole mechanism and linear free energy relationships (LFERs) reported for this reaction series. In this article, an attempt has been made to make the final picture of these non-Malapradian oxidation reactions clear. The kinetic features and applicability of LFERs as well as isokinetic relationship have been discussed. LFER studies indicate the stabilization of positive charge on the aniline nitrogen by resonance and that the transition state formed should be with a considerable positive charge. The reactions are first order in oxidant and substrate and get influenced by ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium. The reactions are characterized by the formation of many intermediates which finally give the benzoquinones i.e. main product. One mol of substrate consumes two moles of periodate in the initial part of most of the reactions. High negative value of entropy of activation is another feature of these reactions which indicates the involvement of solvent interactions in these reactions. Special pH effect has been reported and the rate-pH profile shows a maxima which is characteristic of the aromatic amine oxidized. Rate law explaining the effect of pH and formation of intermediates and the isolated products has been proposed. Gross mechanism and the molecular mechanism have been proposed on the basis of the kinetic features, LFER studies and the identified reaction products.

Keywords : Non-Malapradian oxidation, linear free energy relationships, periodate, aromatic amines, benzoquinones.

Introduction

A detailed survey of literature on periodate oxidation of organic compounds reveals that much work on periodate oxidation of various classes of organic compounds has been carried out from synthesis point of view and a large amount of work on the kinetics of oxidation of 1,2-diols and related compounds (Malapradian oxidation) has been reported and fairly satisfactory picture of mechanism of these processes is available. However, comparatively lesser work on the mechanistic aspect of non-Malapradian oxidations has been carried out and from the work reported so far it is apparent that the mechanism in different cases may be different specially in case of periodate oxidation of aromatic amines. There are two reviews by Sklarz¹ and Dryhurst² available on periodate oxidation of organic

compounds.

Kawashiro^{3,4} reported that arylamine *N*-glucosides react with periodate to form formic acid, formaldehyde and free arylamine is liberated. Further the action of periodate on *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids, aniline, *N*-ethylaniline, *N,N*-diethylaniline, *N*-ethylanilinium hydrochloride, and diphenylamine was studied qualitatively. With the exception of *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines, all the compounds consumed periodate at the same rate as do the α -glycols. It was established that the oxidation of arylamine *N*-glucosides by about five moles of periodate was not due to formic acid or formaldehyde but due to the liberated arylamine itself. However the detailed kinetic and mechanistic studies were not reported.

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Tanabe⁵ also studied a large number of aromatic amines like hydroxylamine, hydrazobenzene and *p*-nitroso-*N,N*-dimethylbenzene which reacted with 1 mole of periodate to form nitrosobenzene, azobenzene and *p*-nitro-*N,N*-dimethylaniline respectively. Several substituted amines and related compounds did not react including *o*- and *p*-aminobenzaldehydes, *o*-nitroaniline, phenylmethylamine and azoxybenzene. Tanabe⁶⁻¹¹ investigated, in some detail, the periodate oxidation of aniline. The oxidation was rapid at pH 1, very slow at pH 9-9.4 and no reaction occurred at pH 12. He suggested that the reaction could be best explained by free radical mechanism. Kaiser and Weidman¹² reported the oxidation of hydroquinone and its monomethyl ether by periodate at pH 1. The reactions were first order in substrate and oxidant and the reaction product was *p*-benzoquinone.

Fialkiewiczowa *et al.*¹³ reported the oxidation of *N*-D-glucosyl-*p*-anisidine, *p*-(D-glucosylamino) azobenzene, *p*-anisidine, *p*-aminobenzene and *p*-formamidoazobenzene by excess of sodium *meta* periodate at different pH. Maximum periodate consumption was at pH 6.2-7.0. 4.6-6.3 moles of periodate was consumed by each mole of *N*-glucoside. Complete oxidative degradation of *N*-glucosylamine followed by the oxidation of liberated free amine was reported. Moehrl *et al.*¹⁴ reported the action of periodate on *o*-anisidine, *m*-anisidine, *p*-anisidine, *N*-ethyl-*p*-anisidine, and *N,N*-diethyl-*p*-anisidine, aldehydes and methanol were detected as the products. No kinetic studies were reported.

Kalinina¹⁵ studied Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of benzidine, *o*-dianisidine and *o*-toluidine by IO₄⁻ in hydrochloric acid containing K₂RuCl₅·H₂O or K₄Ru₂O₇·Cl₁₀. The mechanism of the catalytic effect of ruthenium compounds involved alternate oxidation-reduction of Ru^{III} and Ru^{IV}. Kinetics of uncatalyzed periodate oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline was studied by Pavolva *et al.*¹⁶. Kinetic study of periodate oxidation of aniline in 30 percent aqueous methanol medium was reported by Rao *et al.*¹⁷. They carried out these studies by using iodometric method and also studied substituent effect on this reaction. They reported an ion-dipole interaction for this complex reaction based upon the positive salt effect and the solvent effect on rate as studied by them. They reported a linear Hammett's relationship and the mechanism worked out

by them was in contrast to the earlier findings of Tanabe and Pavolva *et al.* Srivastava *et al.*¹⁸ reported their findings on kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of sulphanilic acid by periodate ion in aqueous medium. They have proposed a mechanism for the formation of azobenzene-4,4-di-sulphonic acid which was isolated and characterized as its *S*-benzyl-isothiouranium derivative.

Mono and dialkyl anilines, toluidines and more slowly halogenoanilines are oxidized by periodate^{3,19}. The rate of the extensive oxidation of phenylenediamines decreases in order *meta* > *ortho* > *para* in contrast to the phenols. Electron withdrawing groups such as -CHO, -COCH₃ and NO₂ retard the oxidation, particularly when placed at *o*- or *p*-position to the amino group. Srivastava *et al.*²⁰⁻²⁵ reported the studies on kinetics and mechanism of periodate oxidation of aniline, *N,N*-dimethylaniline, *o*-xylydine, *p*-aminobenzoic acid and 2,5-dimethylaniline. Their findings were in contrast to the work of Rao *et al.*, Tanabe and Pavolva *et al.*

While Tanabe proposed a free radical mechanism for the reaction between aniline and periodate ion at different pH in his reports, Pavolva *et al.* suggested a free radical mechanism for the periodate oxidation of *N,N*-diethylaniline. On contrary, Rao *et al.* proposed a mechanism involving ion-dipole attack and affirmed that a linear Hammett relationship is being obeyed. Srivastava *et al.*, reported an ion-dipole mechanism for a few aromatic amines in acetic acid-water and acetone-water media. They reported negative salt effect and non-linear Hammett's relationship for the reactions studied. Dryhurst², in his monograph on periodate oxidation of diol and other functional groups has rightly summed up the position when he remarks "Clearly the oxidation of aromatic amines do not follow a very systematic pattern and considerably more compounds need to be studied and further mechanistic studies are desirable".

A study on the comparison of the effect of pH on the uncatalysed periodate oxidation of seven aromatic amines has been reported by Kaushik *et al.*²⁶. Saeed *et al.*²⁷ have reported the conditions for determination of 1-naphthol through periodate oxidation. Anis *et al.*²⁸ reported the kinetic-mechanistic studies on the periodate oxidation of aniline and *o*-chloroaniline. Results of the kinetic study on the oxidation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole by

sodium periodate have been reported by Pradhan *et al.*²⁹. Patra and Misro³⁰ have reported the oxidation of some α -amino acids like glycine and leucine by sodium *meta* periodate in alkaline medium in the absence and presence of Ru^{III}. In contrast to the earlier reports of Rao *et al.*³¹, they suggested a mechanism involving the formation of zwitter ion and assumed it the most probable reactive species. Kaushik *et al.* reported the kinetic-mechanistic studies on the uncatalyzed periodate oxidation of *m*-toluidine³², *p*-toluidine³³, *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-toluidine³⁴, *N*-methylaniline³⁵, *p*-ethylaniline³⁶, *N*-ethylaniline³⁷, 2,4-dimethylaniline³⁸, *o*-ethylaniline³⁹, *o*-toluidine⁴⁰, 3,5-dimethylaniline^{41,48}, *p*-phenetidine⁴², *p*-chloroaniline⁴³, *o*-chloroaniline⁴⁴, *p*-bromoaniline⁴⁵, 2,3-dimethylaniline⁴⁶, *p*-anisidine⁴⁹, *o*-phenetidine⁵⁰, *m*-anisidine⁵¹, 2,5-dimethylaniline⁵², *o*-anisidine⁵³, 3-chloro, 2-methylaniline⁵⁴, *N,N*-diethyl-*m*-toluidine⁵⁵, *N,N*-dimethylaniline and *N,N*-diethylaniline⁵⁶ in acetone-water medium. The role of solvent in these reactions was discussed by them in detail⁴⁷. Effect of substituents on the rate of reaction and testing the validity of linear free energy relationships for a reaction series gives important information regarding the reaction mechanism. The same has also been investigated for uncatalyzed periodate oxidation of anilines^{22,57,58}. Few reports related to the Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of some of the anilines in mixed media⁵⁹⁻⁶⁸ are also available.

Stoichiometry

The absorption maxima of the reaction mixtures are in visible region, while the UV-Vis spectra of IO₄⁻ and substrate indicated these to show no absorption in visible region. Hence, for following the kinetics the absorbance changes were recorded at absorption of reaction mixture at which only the intermediate absorbed. Generally, the progress of the uncatalyzed reaction between periodate of most of the aromatic amines was studied by recording the absorbance of reaction mixture at the predetermined absorption maxima during the period in which the maxima did not change. Reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions at fix pH, ionic strength and dielectric constant of the media. Stoichiometry was evaluated iodometrically. The reactions were observed to take place in many steps with formation of subsequent intermediates/products. The curve obtained in graphical plot between log (*a*-*x*) versus time (where *a*-*x* is the concentra-

tion of unreacted periodate) followed the pseudo-first order behavior up to a point after which the inflexion was obtained. It was taken as the point corresponding to the completion of first stage of reaction for which the kinetic studies were made. The results indicated the stoichiometry to be 1 mole of aromatic amine : 2 moles periodate for the initial part of the reaction. The reaction in case of oxidation of monosubstituted anilines (with substituent group represented by X), can be given as follows :

On mixing the reactants, the solution becomes colored which later changes in to another color. On keeping for long time, it finally gives the product. These observations indicate the formation of more than one intermediate prior to the formation of final reaction product. Plane mirror and the Guggenheim methods, respectively were used for evaluation of initial rates in terms of change in absorbance with time, and pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} . The main reaction products reported in case of oxidation of various aromatic amines are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Main reaction products of periodate oxidation some anilines

Sr. no.	Aromatic amine oxidized	Main reaction product
1.	Aniline	2,5-Dianilino- <i>p</i> -benzoquinoneimine
2.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	4-Bromo-1,2-benzoquinone
3.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyaniline	Ethoxy-1,4-benzoquinone
4.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyaniline	4-Ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyaniline	Methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyaniline	4-Methoxy-1,2-benzoquinone
7.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyaniline	4-Methoxy-1,2-benzoquinone
8.	<i>o</i> -Methylaniline	Methyl-1,4-benzoquinone
9.	<i>p</i> -Methylaniline	4-Methyl-1,2-benzoquinone
10.	<i>m</i> -Methylaniline	4-Methyl-1,4-benzoquinone
11.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	Chloro-1,4-benzoquinone
12.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	4-Chloro-1,2-benzoquinone
13.	<i>o</i> -Ethylaniline	Ethyl-1,4-benzoquinone
14.	<i>p</i> -Ethylaniline	4-Ethyl-1,2-benzoquinone
15.	<i>N</i> -Methylaniline	<i>p</i> -Benzoquinone
16.	<i>N</i> -Ethylaniline	<i>p</i> -Benzoquinone
17.	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaniline	Tautomeric mixture of <i>O</i> -methylquinoneoxime and <i>p</i> -nitrosoanisole

Table-1 (contd.)

18.	<i>N,N</i> -Diethylaniline	Tautomeric mixture of <i>O</i> -ethylquinoneoxime and <i>p</i> -nitrosophenetole
19.	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine	4-Methyl-1,2-benzoquinone
20.	<i>N,N</i> -Diethyl- <i>m</i> -toluidine	Methyl-1,4-benzoquinone
21.	3-Chloro, 2-methyl aniline	2-Chloro, 3-methyl- 1,4-benzoquinone
22.	2,3-Dimethylaniline	2,3-Dimethyl-1,4-benzoquinone
23.	2,4-Dimethylaniline	3,5-Dimethyl-1,2-benzoquinone
24.	2,5-Dimethylaniline	2,5-Dimethyl-1,4-benzoquinone
25.	3,5-Dimethylaniline	2,6-Dimethyl-1,4-benzoquinone

Effect of substituents : Validity of linear free energy relationships

The kinetic data have been utilized by some workers to test the validity of Hammett relationship, its modifications and the isokinetic relationship^{22,57,58}.

These reactions are characterized by a large negative value of entropy of activation ranging from -26.45 to $-266.20 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The decrease in rate with decrease in dielectric constant, and the high negative ΔS^\ddagger values indicate that solvation effects are predominant in these reactions. Since the reactions under study are expected to be ion-dipole type, it is also expected that the entropy of the activated complex for all the substituted anilines should be nearly the same. However, because of the difference in the polarity of different substituted anilines the extent of solvation should be different and hence, the experimental value of ΔS^\ddagger differs from aniline to aniline. Rao *et al.*¹⁷ reported a linear Hammett relationship for the periodate oxidation of anilines in methanol-water medium. In contrast, Srivastava *et al.*²² and Kaushik *et al.*⁵⁸ reported that the Hammett, Exner, Taft, Van Bekkum and Sekigawa plots are non-linear and concave upward while the Brown and Okamoto plot is linear with good correlation coefficient for periodate oxidation of anilines in acetone-water medium. The latter reports are more convincing as these are supported by explanation for special effect of pH (indicating a maxima in rate-pH profile), and perfect rate law as well as the products isolated and characterized by them – features not taken in to account by Rao *et al.*

A non-linear, concave upward Hammett plot indicates that the electron donating substituents stabilize by reso-

nance, a transition state having a high positive charge on the reaction center, which, in this case obviously, is the N of the anilino group. This facilitates the bond breaking process in the transition state. On the other hand, an electron withdrawing substituent increases the capacity of the anilino nitrogen for a more negative charge in the transition state relative to positive charge on the same nitrogen in the ground state. This facilitates the bond making process in the transition state.

If the type of curvature observed in Hammett plot is due to resonance in the transition state, the lower rates should be obtained with the *meta* substituents since it is these substituents that cannot interact through resonance with the reaction site in the transition state. It was observed that the oxidation of many *meta*-substituted derivatives of aniline is quite slow. Thus, from this plot and from the observation that *m*-substituted anilines react much slower, it can be concluded that the transition state is formed in this reaction series with a high positive charge on the anilino nitrogen. The Exner's plot supports this observation.

Linear Brown and Okamoto plot suggests that the transition state formed should be with a considerable positive charge. The non-linear Taft plot and Van Bekkum plot support the involvement of resonance interaction in the oxidation of anilines under consideration. The Sekigawa plot is non-linear indicating thereby that the ionization of anilines is not a deciding step in the reaction mechanism.

The reported value of reaction constant (ρ) obtained from Brown and Okamoto plot is -1.54 . The negative value of ρ suggests that the electron withdrawing groups in the nucleus retard the reaction, while the electron donating groups accelerate it and an electrophilic attack by the periodate ion on the anilino-nitrogen occurs for this oxidation process. A negative value of ρ for the Brown and Okamoto plot further supports the stabilization of positive charge on transition state.

Isokinetic relationship

The reaction series – periodate oxidation of aromatic amines in acetone-water medium shows that the ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger plot is linear indicating thereby that the isokinetic relationship is being followed with isokinetic temperature (β) being 273.27 K ⁵⁷. Rao *et al.*¹⁷ reported a very high

value of 666 K for β for this reaction series in methanol-water medium. Although the values are different, it suggests that the same interaction mechanism may be followed in the oxidation of substituted anilines by periodate ion. However, it may be important to point out that a linear isokinetic relationship with high correlation coefficient does not always indicate the presence of a single interaction mechanism⁷⁰. A straight line may be obtained even in the presence of two interaction mechanisms, if their β values happen to be equal. In spite of the above uncertainties involved, it is reasonable to assume in this case that the same interaction mechanism is probably being followed as other kinetic features and free energy relationships go to support this conclusion.

Rate law and mechanism

The reactions displayed first order in each substrate and oxidant. Rate-pH profile indicated a maximum due to change in the nature of oxidant or substrate species and their relative reactivity when the pH is changed. A change in ionic strength led to a nominal change in the rate while an increase in dielectric constant increased the rate of reaction as indicated by a linear plot between $\log k_2$ versus $1/D$, where D is the dielectric constant of the medium. Both these effects indicate an ion-dipole type interaction in the rate-determining step, and that the reacting ion is possibly an anion. Free radical scavengers acrylamide, allyl acetate and allyl alcohol had no effect on the reaction rate. Thermodynamic parameters have also been reported for these reactions.

In aqueous solutions, periodate exists in three forms governed by the following equilibria :

The value of K_1 indicates that in the pH range 5–9 (in which generally these reactions have been studied) the species H_5IO_6 shall be practically non-existent and hence only species H_4IO_6^- and $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ need to be considered for explaining the observed pH-dependence. In case of aromatic amines, in aqueous solution the following acid-base equilibrium defined by dissociation constant, operates.

In the studied pH-range, both $\text{X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ and $\text{X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$ shall exist.

On starting these reactions, there is appearance of color which continues to darken with increase in the concentration of the intermediate, C and finally the product settles on standing for long time. Obviously, the colored intermediate is formed on a time scale of minutes and the final product on a time scale of hours. The overall reaction involves several steps and possibly several transient intermediates, in addition to comparatively stable one C, are formed during the oxidation. Next, the kinetic order of one in periodate but requirement of the two periodate molecules for each molecule of aromatic amine as per stoichiometry indicates the involvement of only one periodate ion in the rate determining step and second IO_4^- ion is consumed in a fast reaction in the formation of the intermediate, C. It also indicates the intermediate formed prior to the formation of C, is quite stable, and its concentration is not in steady state. Had this been so, there should have been no change in its concentration with time. On the contrary, concentration of C increases continuously with time and reaches a limiting value. Further rate-pH profile indicates the presence of at least three differently reactive reactant species in the pH region chosen for study.

Based on the observed kinetic rate laws and pH-dependence, the following mechanism, which assumes, aromatic amine and H_4IO_6^- to be the reactive species, is proposed.

The intermediate, C, appears to undergo very slow reorganization/hydrolysis to yield the reaction product.

In the mechanism for simplicity, H_4IO_6^- has been written as IO_4^- . Since the elementary reactions in liquid phase are a rarity, the formation of a transient intermediate [C], which could be a collisional complex/reactant

pair in a rapid step having a low value of equilibrium constant, K , is assumed in the proposed gross mechanism.

On considering the values of concentrations of the reactive species in terms of equilibria (2–3) and (4), the complete rate law including $[H^+]$ -dependence becomes:

$$k_2 = \frac{kKK_w [H^+]}{\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2) [H^+] + K_b [H^+]^2\}} \quad (9)$$

where kK is the empirical composite rate constant, K_w is ionic product of water, K_2 is acid dissociation constant of $H_4IO_6^-$ and K_b is base dissociation constant of aromatic amine.

Eq. (9) on rearranging becomes eq. (10).

$$\frac{1}{k_2} = \frac{(K_2/kK[H^+]) + \{(K_w + K_bK_2)/kKK_w\}}{+ K_b [H^+]/kKK_w} \quad (10)$$

The nature of the rate law shows that a plot of $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ shall pass through a minimum⁶⁹. On differentiating $1/k_2$ with respect to $[H^+]$ in eq. (10), the value of $d^2[1/k_2]/d[H^+]^2$ can be obtained. The value of second derivative was found to be positive showing the plot of $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ to pass through a minimum. Thus, on setting $d[1/k_2]/d[H^+] = 0$ for obtaining hydrogen ion concentration at which the $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ profile will pass through minimum, eq. (11) is obtained.

$$[H^+]_{\min} = (K_2K_w/K_b)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

For various substituted anilines, the value of $[H^+]_{\min}$ obtained by substituting the values of K_2 , K_w and K_b in eq. (11) were found to be in good agreement with the experimental value of $[H^+]_{\min}$. This supports the proposed rate law and mechanism for this reaction series.

The molecular mechanism of the reaction proposed in

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 shows the first step as a reversible bimolecular reaction between a *para*-substituted aniline $X-C_6H_4NH_2$ and $[IO_4^-]$. The formation of a charged intermediate complex [A] taking place by the attack of $[IO_4^-]$ on the nitrogen of anilino group and stabilization of positive charge on this nitrogen are well supported by the LFER studies on this reaction series^{22,57,58}. The high negative value of entropy of activation supports the involvement of solvation effects in these reactions. The formation of another intermediate [B] followed by its reaction with another IO_4^- to form quinoneimine [C] in a fast step are the expected steps of the mechanism involved. The last step (10) seems to be the slow hydrolysis and rearrangement of [C] to give benzoquinones [D], i.e. the main product of the reactions reported.

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